

THE MOST IMPORTANT IMPORTANCE OF THE MANGANESE ELEMENT IN THE HUMAN BODY

Jurakulov Javokhir Bakhtiyar o'g'li

Juraqulovjavohir53@gmail.com

**(Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute,
Faculty of Natural Sciences, 2nd year student)**

Abstract: The article discusses the basic properties of manganese (Mn) and its effect on the human body. A systematic review of modern specialized literature and current scientific data was carried out. The best natural sources of manganese are listed. The use of the mineral in various types of medicine and the effectiveness of its use in various diseases are considered. The potential adverse effects of manganese on the human body under certain medical conditions and diseases are analyzed separately.

Keywords: Manganese (Mn), Manganese (Mn) is the 14th, Children, Turamin Manganese, COPD, vitamin D, Doctors.

Manganese is an underrated trace element. It is needed less compared to other minerals, but this does not reduce its role. It is necessary for metabolic processes related to proteins, carbohydrates, glucose and cholesterol. Without microelements, some enzymes cannot function, and the balance of hormones is disrupted. To reap its benefits, just add some foods to your diet. Manganese (Mn) is the 14th most abundant metal on Earth. Included in the group of vital microelements. It is found in almost all types of plant foods. The manganese requirement in the adult body is about 2-4 mg per day. According to many classifications, the element is classified as a heavy metal. Persistent Mn deficiency leads to a decrease in bone mass. The structure and function of joints deteriorate, bones become shorter and thicker. Children may experience growth retardation. The production of sex hormones decreases. Blood glucose levels rise, increasing the risk of diabetes as well as anemia. The role of manganese is important in protecting the skin and preventing rashes. With a lack of manganese, the amount of calcium and phosphorus in the blood increases, which signals problems with bone mineralization. It is noteworthy that with an excess of manganese in the body, the element enters into competition with calcium, which in turn causes bone loss. Workers in hazardous industries, as well as persons with acute intoxication, undergo Mn level diagnostics. Of course, studies are prescribed

by doctors for various diseases caused by deficiency. Patients who have been on parenteral nutrition for a long time are subject to monitoring. The doctor recommends the type of testing. Bioassays used: hair, nails, blood, urine. The benefits of manganese for the body are great, but excess is dangerous and therefore it is necessary to monitor its amount in water and food. Under natural conditions, the element does not exceed physiological norms. In most cases, metal is part of fertilizers and pollutes the environment. In this way, its compounds end up in drinking water. Manganese is neutral and tasteless for humans; it is extremely difficult to determine it without analysis. It will be noticeable only in huge concentrations - the water will acquire a yellow tint and a tart taste. Another source of pollution can be air, where Mn compounds come from metal processing plants. Welding and battery production workers are at risk of poisoning.

- a person experiences weakness, his memory deteriorates;
- at high doses, “manganese madness” is observed, and with chronic exposure, parkinsonism;
- constant fatigue for no apparent reason;
- kidney stones form;
- the functioning of the liver and hormonal system is disrupted;
- allergies, possibly asthma, develop;
- bones become brittle and brittle;
- blood clots form in the vessels.

Children are more susceptible to intoxication. They experience convulsions, low reaction speed, abdominal pain, a fixed gaze (rare movement of the eyelids), and decreased motor activity. The toxic effect of manganese on humans begins at a dose of 40 mg per day. In water, the permissible limit is no more than 0.1 mg per 1 liter. The element manifests its negative effect after several years of intake with water or air, and tends to accumulate. The trace element in its pure form is rarely found in supplements. In pharmacies there is Turamin Manganese from VIS. It contains 2.5 mg of metal. In medicines, Mn is included in prescription complexes for anemia. Manganese (Mn) is an underappreciated micronutrient. The daily requirement is about 2-5 mg - this is relatively little, but despite this its significance is high. Both excess and deficiency affect your well-being. It is necessary to promptly recognize the clinical picture and take measures to eliminate the problem. This requires adjusting your diet or using dietary supplements. You should first consult your doctor to prevent the development of adverse reactions. It is found in large quantities in the liver, brain, kidneys and pancreas. It is an integral

part of many enzymes in the process of digestion and assimilation of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. Deficiency leads to hormone imbalance, hypothyroidism and weight gain. Excess or deficiency is compensated to some extent. Part of the substance obtained from the products moves to the intestines, the excess is excreted with bile. If there is dysfunction in the liver or digestive system, this process is disrupted and there is a risk of poisoning. Separate consideration should be given to the maintenance of cognitive functions. Protecting the brain from oxidative stress prevents disruption of neuronal conduction. Manganese improves the transmission of electronic impulses throughout the body. A sufficient amount of the substance provides support for respiratory health. Together with zinc and selenium, it helps cure COPD (chronic lung disease) by neutralizing the negative effects of oxidizing agents. The protection of lung tissue from the negative effects of respiratory diseases and smoking also increases. Together with calcium, zinc and copper, it strengthens the skeletal system. Together with vitamin D, magnesium and boron, it improves overall bone mass. Effective in combination with glucosamine and chondroitin in the treatment of osteoarthritis. The trace element is necessary for many physiological processes. It plays a role in carbohydrate, protein, lipid and amino acid metabolism. Necessary for the normal functioning of the immune system, regulation of intracellular energy processes and blood clotting, as well as for the growth of connective and bone structures. Normalizes blood sugar levels. Takes part in the formation of insulin, a hormone that controls glucose levels, which prevents the development of gestational diabetes. Supports the formation of platelets and leukocytes. During pregnancy, it is needed in limited quantities; its excess can be harmful. Therefore, it is recommended to obtain manganese from a varied and balanced diet, including foods rich in manganese. Before taking medications, you must discuss this issue with your doctor. Absorption is improved with adequate amounts of vitamin E, K and C, magnesium, zinc and copper. Absorption decreases with an excess of phosphorus, iron and calcium. At normal concentrations, it is possible to fully use and accumulate iron, which prevents the development of anemia. In medicine, manganese is used to prevent and treat deficiency conditions. Doctors prescribe amino acid chelates, gluconate and ascorbate. Manganese supplements are available in capsule, liquid, and injectable forms.

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